

The Role of Workplace Happiness in Achieving Organizational Brilliance a Study on Sadat City University

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Abstract

This paper tries to identify the impact of Workplace Happiness (WH) on Organizational Brilliance (OB) at Sadat City University (SCU) in Egypt. Using Demo & Paschoal, 2016; Paschosl & Tamayo, 2008 for measuring WH and Shobaki & Naser, 2016; O'Shea & Alonso, 2013 for measuring OB. About 400 survey questionnaires were distributed. Multiple follow-ups yielded 300 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 75%.

The research has reached a number of results, the most important of which are: (1) there is a causal relationship between WH and OB. In other words, increasing the level of WH leads to improved OB. The positive impact of WH will encourage workers and motivate them to distinguish the University of Sadat City, (2) the results of the analysis showed that the faculties in SCUy, having increased level of WH, reflect positively on the process of OB, and (3) the results of the analysis showed that WH has a significant impact on OB (brilliance of leaders, brilliance of service and innovation, and brilliance in the field of knowledge).

The research has drawn the following conclusions: (1) the employee's happiness may vary in different cultural contexts. Therefore, further research on happiness issues should be explored to include diverse cultures as well as different types of organizations, (2) the concept of happiness is crucial to organizational performance and productivity. Therefore, HR managers need to design and manage the workplace to promote the employee's happiness, (3) happy staff brings their happiness from the office to their home country. Similarly, they also convey their happiness from their home country to the office. Therefore, this indicates a close relationship between the individual's work and his life, (4) the importance of administrative leadership at SCU to achieve WH, which has a major role in achieving OB, and to bring about positive change within the individual and the organization and society as a whole, (5) it is essential that the administrative leaders of SCU focus on the constraints and limitations that prevent WH, attention to the well-being of employees and the creation of an appropriate environment, as they contribute significantly to the OB of the University, (6) it is essential that the administrative leadership at SCU pays close attention to reducing the process of negative emotional impact, and focus on the positive emotional impact and the achievement of satisfactory work, in order to maintain the level of WH, (7) the attention of the administrative leaders at SCU to positive behaviors that lead to achieving the OB represented by the brilliance of the leaders, the brilliance of service and innovation, and the brilliance of the field of knowledge. There is an essential need to move away from the negative behaviors that limit the process of OB, (8) it is necessary to reward the employees of SCU who enjoy and achieve brilliance in their work and encourage them to provide creative and innovative ideas that contribute to improving the service provided by the university.

1. Introduction

WH is a topic that deserves attention because of the rapid change in the working environment and increased unemployment (Diener, 2000; Peyton & Patricia, 2008; Pillay, 2012).

WH is a complex and mysterious concept. Researchers see 50-80% of happiness as genetic determinants. Organizations, whether public or private, need to study WH, given their growing importance and implications whether at the individual, community or organization level. Many studies of WH have shown that employees with high levels of happiness are more committed or more harmonious at work, (2014).

The issues of happiness have been widely studied in various fields such as philosophy, religion, psychology, sociology, and economics (Aydin, 2012).

Many researchers have discussed the term happiness (Bjorke, 2012; Johnston et al., 2013).

There are two traditional perceptions of happiness in literature. This is the view of hedonic view of eudemonic (Ryan et al., 2008). In other words, academic literature intensifies the definitions of happiness around two main streams. They are hedonic which emphasizes internal self-experiences, such as job

satisfaction - and eudemonic - which emphasizes that expression and self-realization are rooted in well-being (War & Clapperton, 2010).

The hedonic view is one with a long history (Ryan & Deci, 2001). Hedonism tries to maximize pleasure and reduce pain. The pursuit of pleasure is the way to achieve happiness. The expression "Do not worry - be happy" envelops philosophy (Peterson et al., 2005).

The hedonic view of happiness has become more central in the area (Van Horn et al., 2004). There is evidence of eudemonic's superiority in the definition of WH (Dagenis-Desmaris & Savoie, 2012).

In the eudemonic view, happiness comes from identifying virtues and living accordingly. The eudemonic approach sees happiness as different from mere pleasure by assuming that luxury invites people to live according to their real demons or self. This approach sees happiness as a process rather than a state. The eudemonic approach argues that outcomes, although they do not bring immediate pleasure, can promote happiness (Ryan and Desie, 2001).

The eudemonic of happiness involves doing what is virtuous, moral right, true to self, meaningful, and / or productive growth (Reeve and Singer 2008).

Given the importance of both approaches to understanding this phenomenon, the researchers stressed the need to adopt the concepts of happiness that take into account both sides (McNulty & Fincham, 2011; Warr, 2007).

Each of these approaches provides a path to happiness. One can not see them completely independent from each other because people can experience happiness via the hedonic way and the eudemonic route (Ryan et al., 2008).

Well-being is the optimal psychological performance and experience. In literature, well-being is not simply the absence of mental illness. It is more than a simple division of the mental illness and its absence (Ryan & Desie, 2001).

The concept of subjective well-being has become the main focus of welfare studies. It refers to the ways in which people assess their happiness or the quality of their quality of life by using their own perceptions of happiness and well-being (Susniene & Jorkoskas, 2009). SWB is an overall cognitive appraisal of the quality of one's own life (Uchida et al., 2004).

In this research, the term "happiness" is used to include concepts of well-being. Happiness is a high proportion of positive to negative emotions. Therefore, a positive emotional and psychological state distinguishes happiness (Uchida et al., 2004).

2. Workplace Happiness

Happiness is linked to the personal well-being of the individual (Angner et al., 2011; Jiang et al., 2012) or satisfaction with life (Van Praag et al., 2010).

Happiness is universal for all people in every culture because everyone is looking for happiness (Fisher 2010).

Happiness includes many structures; one is that the work involved. This leads to positive organizational results, one of which is Knowledge Brilliance (Monet et al., 2008).

Happy people are more likely to benefit from opportunities in their work environments, as are they more helpful to their colleagues at work, and more confident and optimistic. Unpleasant people are less performing than happy people (Cropanzano & Wright, 2001; Peyton & Patrica, 2008).

Happiness has attracted the attention of philosophers since the dawn of history (McMahon 2006).

Happiness can be defined as the frequent experience of positive emotions. The word happiness has appeared in the literature with multiple names, lasting happiness, positive impact, or self-happiness. During this study, we will use the term happiness in the workplace, where Workplace has a crucial role in the happiness of employees, and if there is hope for individuals to find happiness in their lives, they must find happiness in the workplace. Although the work itself can not make the person happy, the person cannot be really happy if he is unhappy at work. Encouraging the psychological happiness of leaders and employees is, therefore, a good way to enhance individual and organizational performance (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005).

Happiness is one of the words that people disagree about. Some of them see pleasure, comfort, money, office or fame. So many people spend their lives in multiple areas in search of happiness. Happiness is a feeling that comes from within oneself if you feel satisfied and reassured. Happiness and joy, but the views on happiness varied according to their nature, interests, aspirations and even their societies. The greatest

thing for humans is to live a good life in a good society, and all its members feel happy. Happiness and positive situations contribute to greater organizational success and commitment (Gavin & Mason, 2004). Happiness is a universal rule. It reaffirms the life of the individual. Happiness can be considered the best overall assessment is showing some stability over time (Wright, 2002). The rise of positive psychology in the past decade has legitimized attention to happiness and other positive states rather than to the previously dominant disease model, which has drawn disproportionate attention to the disease, depression, stress and similar negative experiences and outcomes (Selegman & Seixentmihali 2000).

Happiness appears in every kind of "basic" human emotion. Feeling happy is essential to the human experience, and most people are at least happy much less time (Diener and Diener 1996). Happiness involves a kind of judgment on the pros and cons of one's life (Parducci, 1995). Happiness is the experience of repeated positive influence, non-repetitive negative impact and a general feeling of satisfaction with life as a whole (Myers & Diner, 1995).

Happiness includes both the relative presence of positive emotions and the relative absence of negative emotions (Diner & Larsen, 1993). Happiness involves activities that convey the feeling of satisfaction, happiness, and positive well-being that make work not only satisfactory but also fun. It goes beyond job satisfaction. As such, job satisfaction can affect WH. In the literature of positive psychology, happiness is treated as a relatively stable self-perception (Diener et al., 1991).

The literature suggests that WH results in different positive organizational outcomes (Monet et al., 2008). Happy organizations have several characteristics: (1) workers are more creative and capable of positive change events; (2) workers do the best they can, not only problem solving, (3) teamwork is encouraged, (4) Of the process of collaboration within the organization (Del et al., 2014; Baker et al., 2006). WH is important for both individuals and organizations (Simmons, 2014), and research on happiness in the organizations is limited (Sloan, 2005). Further investigation should be undertaken to provide sufficient knowledge for academics, practitioners and those concerned with the concept of WH (Hossi et al., 2012). WH is a situation in which the worker is satisfied with his work, and this satisfaction comes from the repetition of positive emotional effects such as joy and pride, and the absence of negative emotional effects such as sorrow and anger (Munoz & Sanz-Vergel, 2013).

WH indicates how people can assess their public lives, and how much people use to govern their lives positively (Tadic et al., 2013).

WH is a self-assessment of the cognitive and emotional life of a person (Borrero et al., 2013).

WH is an individual's sense of joy, satisfaction, and well-being, as well as an individual's sense that his life is meaningful and worthwhile (Pillay, 2012).

WH means the person's love of life, which is positive and gives him a personal sense of well-being (Achor, 2010).

WH includes many different aspects such as participation in work and job satisfaction. These lead to several positive organizational outcomes (Fisher, 2010).

WH focuses on the individual experience of the humanitarian situation at work. It is structured to study labor relations. In other words, it measures the success of an individual's work experience in supporting the individual's psychological well-being and seeking happiness for the individual (Albano, 2009).

WH is the level of the individual's feeling of joy during a given period, influenced by the frequency of positive effects and the absence of negative influences (Singh & Duggal 2008).

WH is the psychological state experienced by the employees of the organization, whether positive or negative, which is reflected in the level of performance of workers in their various jobs (Paschoal & Tamayo, 2008).

WH involves activities that convey a sense of satisfaction, happiness and positive well-being that makes work not only satisfactory but also fun (Fort et al., 2003).

WH refers to an individual's work and satisfaction of life, or well-being at the workplace (Bhattacharjee & Bhattacharjee 2010; Carlton, 2009).

The terms "happiness" and "well-being" are interchangeably used (Frei & Stutzer, 2000).

In this research, we adopted the definition of WH. It is the spread of positive emotions in work and perception by individuals that they express and develop their potential, and progress in achieving their goals. Also, we use the term happiness rather than well-being to emphasize positive aspects, although we do not

rule out the importance of more neutral aspects, such as satisfaction as elements of the overall concept of happiness.

There are three dimensions of WH. They are PA, NA, and FA (Demo & Paschoal, 2016; Paschosl & Tamayo, 2008). These dimensions can be illustrated as follows:

- 1. Positive Affect (PA):** The emotional effect is a set of emotions that face the employees of the organization. The positive emotional impact is the emotions that come from pleasure, excitement and rest are positive effects (Demo & Paschosl, 2016). The positive effect is to show the happy feelings that lead to improved performance, such as joy, pleasure, and pride that are opposite to the negative and sad emotions (Green, 2014). The positive impact is generated by employees as a result of positive practices by leaders in the organization (Calarco, Margaret, 2011). The positive effect refers to the extent to which the person passes a positive emotional state such as happiness, trust, and interest (Singh & Duggal, 2008). It is the positive effect that leads to success and happiness. The positive impact is characterized by many characteristics such as optimism, confidence, self-efficacy, positive social behavior, effectiveness in dealing with challenges, and flexibility in dealing with different issues (Lyubomirsky, King, 2005). People with high levels of positive influence are most involved in the service of the Organization, community building, and assistance to others (Magen & Aharnaoni, 1991). The positive impact is directly correlated with lower employee absenteeism, increased employee job harmony, and those with low positive impact are more likely to quit and struggle with other workers (George, 1989).
- 2. Negative Affect (NA):** the Emotional negative effect is the emotions that come from anxiety, depression, and resentment, all of which represent the negative effects, which lead to the decline of happiness (Demo & Paschoal 2016). Negative influences are a set of negative behaviors used by an employee to elevate his or her own position at the expense of others in terms of their beliefs or sense of self worth, as well as being a source of harm (Green, 2014). Avoiding negative influences leads to the generation of pleasure among employees and contributes to bringing happiness to them (Pillay, 2012). The negative effects are largely related to the decline in individual per capita value (Kirsner et al., 2009). The negative effect refers to the extent to which the person passes a state of negative emotions such as fear and anger (Singh & Duggal 2008). The low negative effect leads to low levels of depression, high daily activity, and therefore impact on the health of mental workers, as workers who are not exposed to the negative impact, they will feel calm and serenity, but if the levels of negative impact, it will generate grief and pain them (Hong et al., 2004). The negative impact leads to lower levels of understanding of life and the meaning of workers (Kirsner et al., 2003). The negative impact leads to a reduction in the confidence of the individual in obtaining a number of friends both inside and outside the organization (Smith & Betz, 2000).
- 3. Fulfillment Affect (FA):** Patient acceptance is the process of perception that relates to the development of workers' skills and potentials in work and progress in achieving their life goals (Demo & Paschoal, 2016). The pursuit of satisfactory acceptance of the individual has become important in society as a legitimate and important aspect of life (Baumeister, 1987). Patient acceptance is happiness and conviction in life. This patient acceptance is synonymous with happiness that accepting patients make people happy with the work they do (Thompson, 2009). There are different situations that lead to happiness, and patient acceptance is one of those essential conditions that lead to happiness (Waterman et al., 2008). In the event of happiness in the workplace, the positive effect tends to have a negative effect, leading to patient acceptance of workers (Paschoal & Tamayo, 2008). There is an ongoing attempt by leaders to attract and retain the special skills of the staff, which can be done by providing the necessary working conditions and ensuring their proper functioning (Warr, 2007).

3. Organizational Brilliance

The pursuit of excellence has become a prerequisite for organizations seeking excellence and competition in the work environment as a result of the rapid change, increasing unrest and globalization (Johnston, 2001). Through tremendous advances in services and technology, organizations are looking for a top-level of excellence, which is known as Organizational Brilliance (OB) (Leslie et al., 2015).

OB can be defined as a high level of excellence by employees as a result of the knowledge, leadership skills and innovation they possess or that distinguish organizations from other organizations in the long term in leadership, service, and knowledge. The difference between excellence and brilliance is that excellence focuses on managing and improving processes, while brilliance focuses on organizational resources,

capabilities and knowledge management that are difficult to imitate to achieve the organization's goals (O'Shea & Alonso, 2013; Terouhid et al., 2016).

There are three dimensions of OB. They are leadership brilliance, service, innovation brilliance, and knowledge brilliance (Al Shobaki & Naser, 2016 O'Shea & Alonso, 2013). These dimensions can be illustrated as follows:

1. **Leadership Brilliance (LB):** It is the most important pillar of modern management. Contemporary management requires the superpower's ability to be able to keep abreast of developments and changes imposed by the age of knowledge. There is no doubt that leaders who have a high sense of familiarity with shortcomings and problems and in all cases have an opportunity to increase competition and thus achieve brilliance.
2. **Knowledge Brilliance (KB):** Many researchers have shown that the qualities that characterize knowledge about other resources of the organization are intangibles. It is difficult to measure and increasingly used in different processes at the same time, on the organization. It can be used for a long time. The university is the first and most important institution that must go to the management of knowledge, in other words: "Universities are the most appropriate institutions to embrace this principle.
3. **Service Brilliance (SB):** Under the management of brilliance, the resort of customers to competitors is a sign that there is a mistake in the way the service and these symptoms lead to the development of a plan of action to correct errors or defects. There is no doubt that using a structured approach to problem solving helps move towards continuous improvement. Brilliance in service and innovation means the development of unique specifications that give the organization an opportunity to set exceptional prices. For example, if a supplier increases input prices, the organization will transfer them to customers. Alternatively, customers can not switch to other organizations for alternative goods and services because of the unique qualities of the organization's products.

4. Research Model

The research framework suggests that WH (independent variable) has an impact on OB (dependent variable) at SCU.

WH is measured in terms of PA, NA, and FA (Demo & Paschoal, 2016; Paschosl & Tamayo, 2008).

OB is measured in terms of LB, SB, and KB (Al Shobaki & Naser, 2016; O'Shea & Alonso, 2013).

Figure (1)

The Research Model

5. Research Questions

The researcher reached to the research problem through two sources. The first is the previous studies that dealt with the relationship between WH and OB. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment in general and SCU in particular.

The second is the pilot study which was conducted with 30 employees at SCU to identify the dimensions of WH and OB. The researcher found several indicators which explain the importance of WH in achieving OB at SCU. The research questions are as follows:

Q1: What is the statistical relationship between WH (PA) and OB at Sadat City University?

Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between WH (NA) and OB at Sadat City University?

Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between WH (FA) and OB at Sadat City University?

6. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between WH and OB.

H1: There is no statistical relationship between WH (PA) and OB at Sadat City University

H2: WH (NA) has no statistically significant effect on OB at Sadat City University in Egypt.

H3: There is no statistical relationship between WH (FA) and OB at Sadat City University.

7. Research Population

The total population at SCU in Egypt is 801 employees. Due to the small number of the research community, it was decided to use complete numeration or census. The research population is illustrated in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Faculty Members	Number	Percentage
1. Faculty of Veterinary Medicine	154	19%
2. Faculty of Tourism & Hotels	93	12%
3. Genetic Engineering Research Institute	124	16%
4. Faculty of Physical Education	186	23%
5. Faculty of Education	49	6%
6. Faculty of Commerce	69	9%
7. Faculty of Law	59	7%
8. Institute for Environmental Studies and Research	50	6%
9. Faculty of Pharmacy	17	2%
Total	801	100%

Source: Staff Members Affairs Department, Sadat University, Egypt, 2018

Table (2) provides more detailed information about the sample and the measures.

Table (2) Frequency Distribution Table of Demographics

Variables	Number	Percentage	
1- Sex	Male	156	52%
	Female	144	48%
	Total	300	100%
2- The Academic Degree	Professor degree	51	17%
	Associate professor	72	24%
	Assistant professor	96	32%
	Lecturer	30	10%
	Demonstrator	51	17%
	Total	300	100%
3- Marital Status	Married	225	75%
	Single	75	25%
	Total	300	100%
4- Age	Less than 30 years	45	15%
	From 30 to 45	135	45%
	More than 45	120	40%
	Total	300	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	144	48%
	From 5 to 10	99	33%
	More than 10	57	19%
	Total	300	100%

8. Data Collection

The researcher has used the questionnaire for collecting data. The questionnaire is interested in WH and OB at SCU. The survey included three questions. The first is related to WH; the second detects OB, the third

relates to the demographic variables of employees at SCU. About 400 questionnaires were distributed. 300 usable questionnaires. The response rate was 75%. The research depends on the Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

9. Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

9.1. Coding of variables

The main variables, sub-variables, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3)
Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables	Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	Workplace	9	Demo & Paschoal, 2016; Paschosl & Tamayo, 2008
	Happiness	12	
		8	
Dependent Variable	Organizational	3	Al Shobaki & Naser, 2016; O'Shea & Alonso, 2013
	Brilliance	3	
		3	

9.2. Construct Validity

The researcher depends on the method of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) in order to verify the quality of the various research measures. CFA was applied to the research variables as follows:

9.2.1. Workplace Happiness

The researcher used CFA for WH which consists of three dimensions. They are PA, NA, and FA. The total number of WH is 29 statement. This can be illustrated by the following figure:

Figure (2)
CFA For WH

From the previous figure, it is clear that all the statement of WH is greater than 0.50, which corresponds to GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. The researcher relies on Structural Equation Model (SEM) because it is the best way to test the compatibility model using AMOS

analysis. The quality indicators for WH variable using AMOS analysis can be illustrated by SEM in the following table:

Table (4)
Quality Indicators for the WH Using AMOS Analysis

Test the Quality of the Model Acceptance Condition ^(*)	Test Value
$X^2 / \text{Degree of freedom} < 5$	3766.962
P. value > 0.5	0.000
Goodness of fit Index (GFI) > 0.90	0.550
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI) > 0.95	0.591
Comparative Fit Index (CFI) > 0.95	0.623
Normed Fit Index (NFI) > 0.90	0.600
Incremental Fit Index (IFI) > 0.95	0.624

^(*) Daire et al., 2008

In light of the above indicators, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

9.2.2. Organizational Brilliance

The researcher used CFA for OB which consists of three dimensions. They are LB, SB, and KB. The total number of OB is 9 statement. This can be illustrated by the following figure:

Figure (3)
CFA For OB

From the previous figure, it is clear that all the statement of OB is greater than 0.50, which corresponds to GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. The researcher relies on SEM because it is the best way to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. The quality indicators for OB variable using AMOS analysis can be illustrated by SEM in the following table:

Table (5)

Quality Indicators for the OB Using AMOS Analysis

Test the Quality of the Model Acceptance Condition ^(*)	Test Value
X ² / Degree of freedom < 5	90.220
P. value > 0.5	0.000
Goodness of fit Index (GFI) > 0.90	0.900

(*) Daire et al., 2008

In light of the above indicators, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

9.3. Descriptive Analysis

Table (6): shows the mean and standard deviations of WH and OB

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
WH	PA	4.00	0.668
	NA	4.18	0.785
	FA	4.00	0.992
	Total Measurement	4.07	0.606
OB	LB	4.30	0.672
	SB	2.93	1.120
	KB	3.45	0.972
	Total Measurement	3.56	0.618

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

According to Table (6), among the various facets of WH, most of the respondents identified the presence of PA (M=4.00, SD=0.668), NA (M=4.18, SD=0.785), and FA (M=4.00, SD=0.992), total WH (M=4.07, SD=0.606).

The second issue examined was the different facets of OB. Most of the respondents identified the presence of LB (M=4.30, SD=0.672), SB (M=2.93, SD=1.120), and KB (M=3.45, SD=0.972), total OB (M=3.56, SD=0.618).

9.4. Evaluating Reliability

Table (7): Reliability of WH and OB

Variables	Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
WH	PA	9	0.887
	NA	12	0.936
	FA	8	0.952
	Total Measurement	29	0.938
OB	LB	3	0.799
	SB	3	0.987
	KB	3	0.874
	Total Measurement	9	0.785

Table (7) presents the reliability of WH and OB. The WH is reliable because ACC is 0.938. ACC for PA is 0.887. ACC for NA is 0.936 while ACC for FA is 0.952. Thus, the internal consistency of WH can be acceptable. Also, the OB is reliable because the ACC is 0.785. ACC for LB is 0.799. ACC for The SB is 0.987 while ACC for KB is 0.874. Thus, the internal consistency of OB can be acceptable.

Accordingly, two scales were defined, WH (29 variables), where ACC represented about 0.938, and OB (21 variables), where ACC represented 0.785.

9.5. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (8): Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	WH	OB
Workplace Happiness	4.07	0.606	1	
Organizational Brilliance	3.56	0.618	0.625**	1

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Regarding Table (8), the level of WH is high Mean=4.07; SD=0.606), while OB is (Mean=3.56; SD=0.618). The overall correlation between WH and OB is 0.625.

9.6. The Correlation between WH and OB

Table (9): Correlation Matrix between WH and OB

Research Variables	1	2	3	4
PA	1			
NA	0.256**	1		
FA	0.371**	0.527**	1	
OB	0.453**	0.492**	0.470**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (9), the correlation between WH (PA) and OB is 0.453. For WH (NA) and OB, the value is 0.492 whereas WH (FA) and OB show correlation value of 0.470.

9.7. Workplace Happiness (PA) and OB

The relationship between WH (PA) and OB is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no statistical relationship between WH (PA) and OB at Sadat City University

Table (10) proves that there is a relationship between WH (PA). It represents 54%, according to MCC. Also, WH (PA) may interpret about 29% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis which states that there is no statistically significant impact of WH (PA) on OO. The alternative hypothesis has been accepted because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between WH (PA) and OB according to T-test.

Table (10): MRA Results for WH (PA) and OB

The Variables of WH (PA)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My work made me feel happy.	0.224**	0.383	0.146
2. My work made me feel excited.	0.000	0.336	0.112
3. My work made me feel cheerful.	0.192**	0.410	0.168
4. My work made me feel enthusiastic	0.013	0.345	0.119
5. My work made me feel proud.	0.234**	0.407	0.165
6. My work made me feel content.	0.059	0.351	0.123
7. My work made me feel willing.	0.073	0.221	0.048
8. My work made me feel calm.	0.128	0.350	0.122
9. My work made me feel active.	0.240**	0.199	0.039
▪ MCC		0.538	
▪ DC		0.290	
▪ CF		13.148	
▪ FD		9, 290	
▪ IF		2.40	
** P < .01	* P < .05		

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

9.8. Workplace Happiness (NA) and OB

The relationship between WH (NA) and OB is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: WH (NA) has no statistically significant effect on OB at Sadat City University in Egypt.

Table (11) MRA Results for WH (NA) and OB

The Variables of WH (NA)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My work made me feel distressed.	0.028	0.377	0.142
2. My work made me feel upset.	0.104	0.486	0.236
3. My work made me feel depressed.	0.081	0.457	0.208
4. My work made me feel jittery.	0.071	0.499	0.249
5. My work made me feel angry.	0.051	0.376	0.141
6. My work made me feel nervous.	0.284**	0.422	0.178
7. My work made me feel frustrated.	0.093	0.184	0.033
8. My work made me feel impatient.	0.091	0.315	0.099
9. My work made me feel annoyed.	0.004	0.315	0.099
10. My work made me feel worried.	0.067	0.435	0.189
11. My work made me feel anxious.	0.425**	0.584	0.341
12. My work made me feel bored.	0.058	0.391	0.152
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ CF ▪ FD ▪ IF 		0.639 0.408 16.471 12, 287 2. 18	
** P < .01		* P < .05	

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (11) proves that there is a relationship between WH (NA). It represents 64%, according to MCC. Also, WH (NA) may interpret 41% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 between WH (NA) and OB according to T-test.

9.9. Workplace Happiness (FA) and OB

The relationship between WH (FA) and OB is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no statistical relationship between WH (FA) and OB at Sadat City University

Table (12): MRA Results for WH (FA) and OB

The Variables of WH FA	Beta	R	R ²
1. I achieve my potential.	0.645**	0.499	0.249
2. I develop abilities that I consider important.	0.567	0.524	0.274
3. I engage in activities that express my skills.	0.078	0.332	0.110
4. I overcome challenges.	0.282*	0.397	0.157
5. I achieve results that I regard as valuable.	0.191	0.503	0.253
6. I advance in the goals I set for my life.	0.306**	0.314	0.098
7. I do what I really like doing.	0.243	0.343	0.117
8. I express what is best in me.	0.226	0.343	0.117
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ CF ▪ FD ▪ IF 		0.582 0.339 18.649 8, 291 2.51	
** P < .01		* P < .05	

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (12) proves that there is a relationship between WH (FA). It represents 58%, according to MCC. Also, WH (FA) interpret about 34% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis which states that there is no impact of WH (FA) on OB. The alternative hypothesis has been accepted because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 between WH (FA) and OO according to T-test.

10. Research Results

1. There is a causal relationship between WH and OB. In other words, increasing the level of WH leads to improved OB. The positive impact of WH will encourage workers and motivate them to distinguish SCU.

2. The results of the analysis showed that the faculties in SCU, which increases the level of WH, it reflects positively on the process of OB.
3. The results of the analysis showed that WH (PA, NA, and FA) has a significant impact on OB (LB, SB, and KB) at SCU.
4. The researcher used CFA in order to verify the quality of the various research measures. It is clear that all the statement of WH and OB are greater than 0.50, which corresponds to the GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. In addition to that, the researcher depends on SEM because it is one of the best ways to use the multivariable test. SEM has been used to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. In order to ascertain whether the model is compatible with the sample data used. Also, it already measures the variable that should be measured. In general, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

11. Recommendations

1. The employee's happiness may vary in different cultural contexts. Therefore, further research on happiness issues should be explored to include diverse cultures as well as different types of organizations.
2. Activating the role of university academic guidance, publish academic guidance among students, submit academic plans to the faculty department, overcome ambiguity in academic systems for students who have not been identified, seek extension services, hold regular lectures to identify students and correct registration method, new study.
3. The concept of happiness is crucial to organizational performance and productivity. Therefore, HR managers need to design and manage the workplace to promote the employee's happiness.
4. Staple university care centers for gifted and talented students follow up their growth and creativity after graduating from university and work in the production sectors.
5. Happy staff members bring their happiness from the office to their home country. They convey their happiness from their home country to the office. Therefore, this indicates a close relationship between the individual's work and his life.
6. Providing adequate equipment in the public lecture halls, enhancing ventilation, lighting inside the lecture hall, and work on the development of playgrounds such as spaces and sports tools.
7. The importance of administrative leadership at SCU to achieve WH, which has a major role in achieving OB, and to bring about positive change within the individual and the organization and society as a whole.
8. Providing the library of the college with modern references in all disciplines, focusing on the specializations available in the college periodically each year, providing electronic services and research sites benefiting students and faculty members, and increasing library holdings.
9. It is essential that the administrative leaders of SCU focus on the constraints and limitations that prevent WH, attention to the well-being of employees and the creation of an appropriate environment, as they contribute significantly to the OB of the University.
10. Development of the database in the Central University Library, with the expansion of the library and increase the capacity of students.
11. It is essential that the administrative leadership at SCU pay close attention to reducing the process of negative emotional impact, and focus on the positive emotional impact and the achievement of satisfactory work, in order to maintain the level of WH.
12. It is essential to choose the methods of teaching that are appropriate to the technology and communication revolution in proportion to the large numbers and nature of students.
13. The attention of the administrative leaders at SCU to positive behaviors that lead to achieving the OB represented by the brilliance of the leaders, the brilliance of service and innovation, and the brilliance of the field of knowledge. There is an essential need to move away from the negative behaviors that limit the process of OB.
14. It is necessary to reward the employees of SCU who enjoy and achieve brilliance in their work and encourage them to provide creative and innovative ideas that contribute to improving the service provided by the university.

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